

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

ISSUE 5

 Acceptance of papers **May, 2026**

Acceptance of papers
Published monthly

Topics
economics,
technology, social sciences

ISSN 3060-5229

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THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR ELECTRONIC
JOURNAL **"INNOVATION SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY"** HAS BEEN REGISTERED
UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

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The scientific electronic journal "Innovation Science and Technology" has been included in the list of scientific publications recommended for the publication of main scientific results of dissertations for the award of PhD and DSc degrees in economics and technical sciences, in accordance with the Resolution No. 370 of the Presidium of the Higher Attestation Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated May 8, 2025.

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THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES ON WOMEN'S LABOR IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES OF UZBEKISTAN UNDER INDUSTRY 4.0

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Abstract. This article analyzes the mechanisms through which digital and innovative technologies influence women's labor in industrial enterprises of Uzbekistan under the conditions of Industry 4.0. The study examines the impact of artificial intelligence, robotics, the Internet of Things, big data, and cloud-based platforms on the structure of female employment, occupational mobility, and skill requirements. The research is based on data from international organizations (ILO, World Bank, WEF) and the legislative framework of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is argued that technological transformations simultaneously create new opportunities while also potentially deepening existing gender disparities. Practical recommendations aimed at expanding women's participation in innovation-driven industrialization are proposed.

Keywords: Industry 4.0, digital economy, women's labor, industrial enterprises, innovative technologies, artificial intelligence, automation, gender equality, digital skills, Uzbekistan.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Sanoat 4.0 sharoitida raqamli va innovatsion texnologiyalarning O'zbekiston sanoat korxonalaridagi ayollar mehnatiga ta'sir mexanizmi tahlil qilinadi. Sun'iy intellekt, robototexnika, buyumlar interneti, katta ma'lumotlar va bulutli platformalar kabi texnologiyalarning ayollar bandligi tarkibiga, kasbiy harakatchanligiga hamda malaka talablariga ta'siri yoritilgan. Tadqiqot xalqaro tashkilotlar (XMT, Jahon banki, JIF) ma'lumotlari va O'zbekiston Respublikasining normativ-huquqiy bazasiga asoslanadi. Texnologik o'zgarishlar bir tomondan yangi imkoniyatlarni yaratishi, ikkinchi tomondan esa mavjud gender tafovutlariga ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkinligi asoslab berilgan. Ayollarning innovatsion industrializatsiyadagi ishtirokini kengaytirishga qaratilgan amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Sanoat 4.0, raqamli iqtisodiyot, ayollar mehnati, sanoat korxonalari, innovatsion texnologiyalar, sun'iy intellekt, avtomatlashtirish, gender tengligi, raqamli ko'nikmalar, O'zbekiston.

Аннотация. В статье анализируется механизм влияния цифровых и инновационных технологий на женский труд на промышленных предприятиях Узбекистана в условиях Индустрии 4.0. Раскрыто воздействие искусственного интеллекта, робототехники, интернета вещей, больших данных и облачных платформ на структуру женской занятости, профессиональную мобильность и требования к квалификации. Исследование основано на данных международных организаций (МОТ, Всемирный банк, ВЭФ) и нормативно-правовой базе Республики Узбекистан. Обосновано, что технологические изменения одновременно создают новые возможности и в то же время способны усиливать существующие гендерные различия. Сформулированы практические рекомендации по расширению участия женщин в инновационной индустриализации.

Ключевые слова: Индустрия 4.0, цифровая экономика, женский труд, промышленные предприятия, инновационные технологии, искусственный интеллект, автоматизация, гендерное равенство, цифровые навыки, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

The modern global economy is undergoing fundamental transformations under the conditions of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, commonly referred to as Industry 4.0. Technologies such as artificial intelligence, robotics, the Internet of Things, big data analytics, and cyber-physical systems are reshaping industrial production, labor organization, and skill requirements within enterprises [1-2]. These changes are generating structural transformations and have a significant impact on women's labor in the industrial sector.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, industry and the digital economy are being actively developed within the framework of the "Uzbekistan – 2030" Strategy and the "Digital Uzbekistan – 2030" Strategy [3-4]. In this

process, expanding women's participation in industrial labor has become one of the important directions of state socio-economic policy. Law No. O'RQ-562, and other regulatory documents during 2018–2023 created an institutional basis for ensuring gender equality [5-6].

At the same time, the impact of Industry 4.0 technologies on women's labor has a complex and multidimensional character. On the one hand, technological innovations create new opportunities for women, including access to highly skilled occupations, flexible working arrangements, and innovative entrepreneurship.

The purpose of this article is to analyze the mechanism through which Industry 4.0 technologies influence women's labor in industrial enterprises of Uzbekistan and to develop evidence-based recommendations. The main objectives of the study are: (1) to identify the main channels through which Industry 4.0 technologies affect industrial development; (2) to assess the impact of these technologies on women's labor in terms of opportunities and risks; (3) to examine Uzbekistan's institutional framework in this area; and (4) to formulate recommendations for gender-inclusive innovative industrialization.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of Industry 4.0 was developed by Klaus Schwab and is defined as the integration of digital, physical, and biological technologies [1]. Erik Brynjolfsson and Andrew McAfee demonstrated that the Fourth Industrial Revolution leads to structural transformations in the labor market and fundamentally changes skill requirements [2]. The World Bank, in its *World Development Report 2019*, provided a detailed analysis of how technological change is reshaping the nature of work [7].

Significant research on the gender dimensions of technological transformation has been conducted by the International Labour Organization (ILO), the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), and the World Economic Forum (WEF). The ILO's *World Employment and Social Outlook 2024* report highlights that technology and automation affect women's and men's labor differently [8]. Similarly, the WEF's *Global Gender Gap Report 2024* emphasizes the continuing underrepresentation of women in STEM and artificial intelligence-related fields [9].

From a theoretical perspective, this issue can also be explained through Claudia Goldin's concept of gender convergence. According to the author, the reduction of gender disparities is closely associated with changes in occupational structures and working-time arrangements [10]. Joan Acker's theory of "gendered organizations" further demonstrates how internal organizational structures within industrial enterprises may reproduce gender inequalities [11].

In the context of Uzbekistan, this topic remains relatively underexplored. Karabaeva G. Sh. analyzed the prospects for the development of innovative processes in Uzbekistan's industrial sector [12]. In addition, specialized ILO studies on particular industrial branches — including textile, food-processing, and light industries — revealed the gender dimensions of labor conditions and technological transformations within these sectors [13]. However, the specific impact of digital technologies on women's labor has not yet been sufficiently studied as an independent research subject. This article seeks to contribute to filling this research gap.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research is based on a combination of structural and institutional analysis methods. The study consists of several stages: (1) classification of Industry 4.0 technologies and their areas of application in industry; (2) assessment of the impact of each technology on women's labor in terms of opportunities and risks; (3) examination of the strategic and legal framework of the Republic of Uzbekistan; and (4) formulation of practical recommendations.

The study applies comparative analysis, systematic analysis, institutional analysis, and analytical generalization methods. Particular attention is given to identifying the relationship between technological transformation, labor-market restructuring, and gender dimensions within industrial enterprises. The analysis also considers the influence of digitalization on employment structure, professional mobility, qualification requirements, and women's participation in innovation-oriented sectors.

The empirical sources include data from the International Labour Organization (ILOSTAT), the World Bank's *World Development Report*, the WEF *Global Gender Gap Report*, OECD publications, the National Database of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan (lex.uz), and official statistics published by the Statistics Agency of Uzbekistan. The analytical period covers 2017–2024 and includes the implementation of major institutional reforms and digital transformation strategies in Uzbekistan.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The main technological directions of Industry 4.0 — including artificial intelligence, robotics, the Internet of Things, big data, and cloud-based platforms — are reshaping the operational processes of industrial enterprises, labor organization, and qualification requirements. These technologies increase production efficiency, improve resource management, optimize decision-making processes, and accelerate digital transformation within enterprises.

The characteristics of the main Industry 4.0 technologies, their areas of industrial application, and their impact on women's labor are systematized in Table 1.

Table 1
Industry 4.0 Technologies and Their Impact on Women's Labor¹

Technology	Main areas of industrial application	Impact on women's labor
Artificial intelligence and machine learning	Optimization of production processes, quality control, predictive analytics	Creates new highly skilled jobs; however, gender disparities may persist due to women's lower participation in STEM occupations
Robotics and automation	Assembly lines, packaging, material handling, precision processing	Reduces physical labor intensity, but routine jobs in textile and food-processing industries may face automation risks
Internet of Things (IoT) and cyber-physical systems	Real-time equipment monitoring, energy efficiency, occupational safety	Improves working conditions; creates demand for new technical specializations
Big data and analytical systems	Analysis of production efficiency, demand forecasting, logistics	Opens new opportunities in analytical and managerial occupations; increases demand for digital skills
Cloud services and digital platforms	Inter-enterprise cooperation, remote work, ERP/CRM systems	Expands flexible work arrangements and improves work-family balance opportunities for women
Additive manufacturing (3D printing)	Prototyping, customized production, spare-parts manufacturing	Creates new entrepreneurial opportunities and expands women's participation at the micro- and small-enterprise levels

Source: compiled by the author based on [1-2; 7-8].

As can be seen from the table, digital technologies simultaneously create new highly skilled jobs while also posing challenges to traditional routine occupations. In academic literature, this dual impact is commonly referred to as the "polarization effect," whereby the share of highly skilled jobs increases, while medium-skilled routine occupations gradually decline. Since women have traditionally been highly represented in medium-skilled routine industrial jobs — particularly in textile manufacturing, food-processing industries, and electronics assembly — they are more significantly exposed to this effect [7].

The transition to Industry 4.0 significantly changes qualification requirements within industrial enterprises. A comparative analysis of the traditional industrial labor structure and the skills required under Industry 4.0 conditions is presented in Table 2.

Table 2
Skills Required in Industrial Enterprises Under Traditional and Industry 4.0 Conditions²

Direction	Traditional skills (under Industry 3.0 conditions)	Skills required under Industry 4.0 conditions
Technical skills	Operating mechanical equipment; specialization in a single product type; manual monitoring	Working with automated systems, sensors, and robotics; real-time data monitoring

1 Author's development

2 Author's development

Digital literacy	Limited to basic office software skills (Word, Excel)	Working with production databases, ERP/MES systems, and artificial intelligence platforms
Analytical ability	Reading standard reports and statistical data	Big data analysis, predictive analytics, visualization, and decision-support systems
Communication and collaboration	Face-to-face internal communication; traditional management hierarchy	Working in remote and hybrid teams; cross-functional collaboration through digital platforms
Problem-solving	Following standard procedures and instructions	Analyzing unstructured situations; independent decision-making; systems thinking
Learning and adaptability	One-time vocational training; narrow professional specialization	Lifelong learning; upskilling and reskilling; multi-skilled professional development
Innovative thinking	Focused on maintaining existing processes	Searching for innovative solutions; experimentation; openness to change

Source: compiled by the author based on [1-2; 7-8; 14].

As can be seen from Table 2, the skills required under Industry 4.0 conditions differ significantly from traditional technical competencies. This transformation creates both opportunities and challenges for women’s labor simultaneously. On the one hand, digital skills and analytical competencies often rely more on knowledge and professional qualifications than on physical strength, thereby expanding women’s access to highly skilled industrial occupations.

The implementation of Industry 4.0 technologies in industrial enterprises is not a one-time action but rather a complex and gradual process carried out in several stages. Figure 1 illustrates the main stages of this process and highlights the importance of integrating the gender dimension at each stage.

Figure 1 – Stages of Industry 4.0 Implementation in Industrial Enterprises³

The first stage — diagnosis and assessment — includes analyzing the enterprise’s technological condition, workforce preparedness, and, importantly, the gender distribution within the workforce. The second stage — strategy and roadmap development — covers setting objectives, selecting appropriate technologies, and

³ Source: compiled by the author.

planning investments. The third stage — implementation of pilot projects — involves conducting limited-scale testing and organizing workforce training. The fourth stage — phased implementation — consists of expanding technological adoption and carrying out comprehensive retraining programs. The fifth stage — full integration and monitoring — ensures sustainable operations, KPI monitoring, and continuous improvement. Integrating the gender dimension at all stages is an essential prerequisite for ensuring equal opportunities for women and promoting the development of STEM-related skills.

The “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” Strategy (Resolution No. PQ-4699) [1] and the “Uzbekistan – 2030” Strategy established a strategic foundation for the development of the digital economy and industrial modernization. Institutions such as IT Park Uzbekistan, Technopark, and other innovation ecosystem organizations play an important role in strengthening technological capacity. Programs aimed at developing digital skills, including *One Million Uzbek Coders*, also create opportunities for women to participate more actively in the digital economy. At the same time, assessing the gender effectiveness of these programs requires the introduction of systematic gender-disaggregated monitoring mechanisms.

The impact of Industry 4.0 on women’s labor is manifested through four main channels.

The first channel is the transformation of skill requirements. Industrial enterprises increasingly demand hybrid qualifications that combine technical knowledge with digital competencies. This creates new highly skilled employment opportunities. However, because women’s participation in STEM professions remains relatively low, there is a risk that they may not benefit equally from these opportunities [9].

The second channel is automation and job displacement. Routine operations in textile, food-processing, and electronics assembly industries are particularly vulnerable to automation. Since women represent a relatively large share of employment in these sectors, the implications of automation are especially significant from a gender perspective [7-8].

The third channel is the emergence of flexible forms of employment. Digital technologies facilitate remote work, hybrid working arrangements, and platform-based employment opportunities. These developments may help women better balance professional and family responsibilities. At the same time, new challenges may arise, including intensified labor processes, weaker social protection, and the growing need for permanent online connectivity.

The fourth channel is innovative entrepreneurship. Digital platforms and technoparks create new entrepreneurial opportunities for women. In micro- and small-enterprise sectors, areas such as 3D printing, digital marketing, and e-commerce provide women with opportunities to establish and manage businesses with relatively low entry barriers.

The analysis demonstrates that the impact of Industry 4.0 technologies on women’s labor has a dual character. Without well-designed and targeted policy measures, existing gender disparities may become more pronounced. Therefore, ensuring that innovative industrialization develops in a gender-inclusive manner and preventing the negative effects of technological determinism should become an important national priority.

Uzbekistan’s institutional framework — including Presidential Decree No. PF-5325, Law No. O’RQ-562, Resolution No. PQ-4699, and Presidential Decree No. PF-158 — provides a solid foundation for this transformation process. However, a gap still exists between the objectives outlined in strategic policy documents and their implementation at the level of industrial enterprises. To reduce this gap, it is necessary to introduce enterprise-level monitoring systems, gender-disaggregated statistical databases, and clear accountability mechanisms.

International experience is also highly significant in this regard. The European Union and OECD countries have accumulated substantial experience in integrating the gender dimension into Industry 4.0 strategies [14]. STEM education initiatives, digital-skills training programs for women, and enterprise-level mentoring systems are among the approaches that could be effectively adapted to the conditions of Uzbekistan.

Thus, the effectiveness of Industry 4.0’s impact on women’s labor largely depends on complementary policy measures, including reforms in education, labor-market policies, social protection systems, and the integration of inclusive corporate ecosystems. Relying solely on legal reforms would not be sufficient to ensure sustainable and inclusive outcomes.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the study, the following main conclusions can be drawn.

First, the Republic of Uzbekistan has established a solid strategic and legal framework for the development of the digital economy and the promotion of gender equality. The “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” and “Uzbekistan – 2030” strategies, together with Law No. O’RQ-562, constitute an important institutional foundation in this direction.

Second, the impact of Industry 4.0 on women's labor is manifested through four main channels: changing skill requirements, automation, flexible forms of employment, and innovative entrepreneurship. Each of these channels generates both opportunities and challenges.

Third, achieving gender-inclusive innovative industrialization requires a comprehensive approach that extends from strategic policy documents to enterprise-level implementation practices.

Based on the findings of the research, the following recommendations are proposed:

Implement targeted programs aimed at expanding women's participation in STEM education, particularly in industrial engineering, artificial intelligence, and data analytics.

Introduce digital-skills retraining programs at the enterprise level, including special quotas or incentives for women.

Expand active labor-market policies and retraining programs for workers in textile and food-processing industries, where the risks associated with automation are relatively high.

Integrate the gender dimension into the implementation of the "Digital Uzbekistan – 2030" Strategy through gender-disaggregated monitoring and reporting mechanisms.

Develop specialized financial and consulting mechanisms to support women's entrepreneurship and innovative start-ups in cooperation with the ecosystems of IT Park Uzbekistan and technoparks.

Introduce mentoring systems and career-development programs for women in industrial enterprises to increase their representation in enterprise management.

Promote a gender-inclusive workplace culture through flexible working arrangements, work–family balance policies, and mechanisms aimed at preventing workplace discrimination and pressure.

Future research may focus on enterprise-level empirical surveys, panel data analysis, and comparative studies involving Central Asian countries. Such studies would contribute to developing practical evidence-based approaches for supporting the implementation of the "Uzbekistan – 2030" and "Digital Uzbekistan – 2030" strategies.

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Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV
Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2026. № 5

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